

SPEAKING SKILLS OF TEACHERS IN DEVELOPING THE INTERESTS OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Annotation. In this article, various methods and forms of making students interested in the basics of science are highlighted in pedagogical and special methodical literature, including creating interesting situations during the lesson, organizing lessons with didactic games, improving speech in many ways. Is devoted to the analysis of the individual psychological characteristics of the teacher.

Key words: pedagogy, psychology, method, primary class.

Аннотация. В данной статье в педагогической и специальной методической литературе освещены различные методы и формы заинтересованности учащихся основами науки, в том числе создание интересных ситуаций на уроке, организация уроков с помощью дидактических игр, совершенствование речи по многим направлениям. Посвящено анализу индивидуально- психологических особенностей учителя.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, психология, методика, начальный класс.

Introduction. It is a complex didactic process to interest students in the basics of various subjects from the teacher to the students in class and extracurricular activities great pedagogical and psychological knowledge is required on organization issues is enough. Levels of interest of students of a certain class in certain science basics it is different and manifests itself in different characters. Students' interest the lowest stage; in relation to the information, they receive in the course of the lesson. It manifested in the interests that have arisen. Such interest, the passage of time. It has developed to its new stage - important subjects and events can arise in the process of studying its features.

Pedagogical and special methodical literature guides students to the basics of science various methods and forms of interest are highlighted, among them, in particular, creating interesting situations during the lesson, didactic games on the basis of organizing lessons, inter-subject communication as the most effective methods of such forms as wide use of opportunities recognized. Obviously, such methods give only theoretical knowledge. It is appropriate in not only the process, but also when it used for practical training gives good results. It is interesting for students during the lessons there are enough potential opportunities to create situations and the wide use of connections between educational subjects is also in this regard gives significant positive results.

In the implementation of interdisciplinary communication success is determined by two conditions: the first is in interrelated disciplines the second is that the main concepts are interpreted in the same sense on the issues that need to be resolved in the formation of concepts, to ensure the necessary sequence and consistency between disciplines, as well as redundancy it is the presence of clear coordination in order not to leave room for returns. Usually, the conditions for enjoying research methods of scientific creators are different: for example, for some scientists it is satisfaction from their work, and for others it is a duty to students and fellow citizens.

It is known that when a student has interest in knowledge, demand, commitment, only if he feels the feelings of duty, he accepts the content of the given lesson and remembers Properly organized teaching, students have this knowledge sparks his interest and this knowledge is remembered. Many according to the opinion of the researchers give an example of the topic being taught when the lesson is taught, the students are less tired. Again, the student's encouragement also plays an important role in their interest in the lesson. The concept of motivation is "demand for learning" and "interest in learning". Stands side by side with the concept.

Encourages students to learn, the main factor of interest is this - motivation. Due to the versatility of motivation, psychologists divide it into two types, i.e

conditionally; they divided into external and internal types. External stimulation is this rewarding, awarding, scaring students, etc. In this case knowledge getting family is not considered a goal, but the goal is praise in any way, it remains to receive a reward, and in the case of not being able to achieve these, it is the responsibility of the student psychological stress, an unhealthy situation arises. After all, it is different uses cribs, is indifferent to studying. The main goal of internal motivation is to acquire knowledge. Internal motivation of students interested in learning. (Problem solving, experimenting, scientists learning discoveries, etc.). Internal from the point of view of pedagogy. It was found to be one of the optimal methods of motivation and teaching. This is the method students do not experience psychological stress. To study in them, independently encourages thinking, to gain knowledge by struggling with oneself, to be interested. But these are the methods to make students interested in reading I should not limit myself. They are trained and developed issues, society and the demands and needs of students personally it is necessary to teach taking into account.

Students' activities in the process of teaching academic subjects —if we touch on the issue of activation, the psychology of acquiring knowledge —thinking created by a problematic situation is the greatest will have activation. Creating a problem situation, lesson that it has important advantages over a simple explanation of its purpose proven. In such a situation, students learn the importance of the lesson creates motives that lead to conscious mastery. The ability to speak is the ability to express one's feelings and emotions through speech together with the use of mime and pantomime to express clearly and clearly ability. This is mainly information transmitted from the teacher to the students the second signal system is given by speech. In terms of content, it is his internal and external features are meant.

Loudness of speech - speaking loudly also scores the same points will come. Excessively harsh, sharp, shouting speech annoys the student's touches, quickly exhausts them and causes protective braking. This is where Nasriddin Tusi, one of the eastern thinkers, "... teacher speech should never and anywhere be venomous,

rude or harsh not allowed. A teacher's lack of self-control during a lesson can disrupt work it would be very appropriate to quote his advice that it is possible... Teacher's empty, low voice sounds bad. Speech, gestures, various sharp movements enlivens the students. In this way gestures and actions are experienced used by teachers in moderation. But the same relentless too much movement gets on one's nerves.

Public education in the conditions of an independent republic is unique going through a period of development. This uniqueness is primarily the nationalization of the content of education, that is, our very rich past history, culture, science, and language with their essence. Educating the young generation, who are the future of our society, on the basis of our national traditions, which have a very beautiful, high human moral content we were lucky. This is for all of us teachers it forms high feelings of pride in our hearts. This means a new approach to the educational process, a new style and content, form and requires us to use the tools as well. New with old style tasks cannot be performed.

It is known that the traditional teaching method is widespread in our country.

However, the implementation of reforms in the field of education is traditional that important educational problems of education are not being solved and that a number of advanced pedagogical experiences are not being popularized we can see. So doing it with the old traditional method it won't happen. Therefore, we think that this issue is a new pedagogy can be done on the basis of technology.

Recently, "Advanced teacher", "Advanced teacher", "Innovator pedagogue" concepts in the press pages, pedagogues exchange multilingual in conversations, methodological councils, seminars and conferences not available, but based on them is not very new. "Advanced pedagogue" first of all looks at his work more responsibly than other teachers. That's it learning from positive experiences in the field in their lessons and from the classroom laughs at extracurricular activities. Through this, students achieves certain achievements in education and upbringing.

Study their serious sources and work on their basis if you go look with a critical eye at the sources that have a creative teacher knows in many cases, their

attitude to existing methodological guidelines according to the conditions and the situation, according to his capabilities uses methodological methods different from existing procedures. Advanced should be based on certain criteria when determining pedagogical experiences. In this case, the most important criterion is used by the teacher in his pedagogical activity is a new form, method and method of education. This criterion is Advanced is the most important feature that distinguishes a teacher from ordinary teachers. The innovation used by the teacher is different, for example, education or upbringing new content, form, method, the most impressive of pedagogical work may consist of determining ways of improvement. An advanced pedagogue is not an individual experience, but a mass experience formed experiences, with the work style of other teachers. The fact that it is composed on the basis of succession increases its effectiveness and facilitates its spread. Pedagogical skills include pedagogy takes the technique.

Another important component of pedagogical technique is the pedagogue are mimic, pantomimic movements. Clear gesture, face-eyes, body a gesture, a meaningful look, an encouraging or sincere smile has a greater pedagogical impact than verbal explanations. can be an effective means of communication. Acquisition of pedagogical techniques ensures that the teacher can have the best educational effect. It is a condition for the teacher to save his energy and time and work creatively creates. Pedagogical sensitivity and understanding are also pedagogical skills is important in acquisition. Pedagogical skills are pedagogical the most important, subtle part of the technique is the impact with the word does. In the process of pedagogical creativity, education is completely new development of approach, new form, methodological method, tools justifying their use in new conditions or their new theoretical and methodological improvement based on the requirements of tasks includes stages such as applying conclusions to the pedagogical process.

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